

Molybdenum co-factor deficiency (MOCS2): A rare case report delineating as severe neonatal presentation as hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy due to Molybdenum cofactor deficiency / isolated sulfite oxidase deficiency

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: We report a infants with the diagnosis of molybdenum cofactor deficiency. The key findings leading to diagnosis were intractable neonatal seizures unresponsive to treatment, craniofacial dysmorphic features, hypotonia, low blood uric acid levels, and neuroimaging findings. The parents were consanguineous in this case report . The diagnosis was established by the presence of low blood uric acid levels and detection of urinary chloride. Magnetic resonance imaging findings were suggestive of encephalomalacia with cystic changes with multiple white matter hemorrhage due to hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy. We conclude that molybdenum cofactor deficiency must be included in the differential diagnosis of patients presenting with intractable seizures, unexplained vomiting with hypotonia in the newborn period who have computed tomography and magnetic resonance imaging findings reminiscent of those of hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy, and the urine sulfite dipstick test can be a part of the evaluation of these infants in neonatal intensive care units.

Objectives: To delineate clinical manifestations and diagnostic approach in case of Molybdenum cofactor deficiency (MoCS2) isolated sulfite oxidase deficiency in neonate.

Background: 24 day old female child with severe distress, seizure in altered consciousness presented to ER and was intubated, primary treatment given. Status was managed per protocol (ILAE), and classified to be SE. Child was sedated, ventilated and investigated for same. Blood chemistries and counts were non specific for infection, electrolyte and metabolic disturbances at ER. Blood investigation for ABG was reported abnormal and corrected accordingly. Work up for ammonia was normal. Child remained encephalopathic hence study

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proceed with neuroimaging. USG skull normal. MRI s/o Cystic encephalomalacia with In subcortical white matter in frontoparietal and temporal Lobes with bilateral Subdural collection, Punctate white matter hemorrhage In bilateral periventricular White matter. These findings given in clinical settings given rise to a suspicion of molybdenum cofactor deficiency (MOCD)/isolated sulfite oxidase Deficiency. Further findings were confirmed by DNA report study of whole exome suggestive for MOCS2 gene mutation positive.

Conclusions: Molybdenum cofactor deficiency is a severe autosomal-recessive disorder with a devastating outcome. This disorder is caused almost exclusively by mutations in the MOCS1 or MOCS2 genes. Mutations affecting this biosynthetic pathway result in a lethal phenotype manifested by progressive neurological damage via the inactivation of the molybdenum cofactor-dependent enzyme, sulfite oxidase. IEM is individually rare but collectively common, Though IEM is criteria for exclusion but as clinicians we should keep investigating as MOCD is rare but having grave prognosis once diagnosed. Molecular diagnosis and genetic counseling, Parental counselling for future pregnancy is essential. Algorithmic approach will help to clinch the diagnosis.

Keyword: Molybdenum, deficiency (MOCS2), hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy

INTRODUCTION:

Molybdenum cofactor deficiency in an infant presenting with intractable neonatal seizures, and a severe progressive encephalopathy. This is a rare disease entity that can be easily missed or confused with hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy and have grave prognosis once diagnosed. Molybdenum cofactor deficiency (MoCD) is an autosomal recessive disorder, which causes the combined deficiency of molybdenum-dependent enzymes, including sulfite oxidase, xanthine dehydrogenase, and aldehyde oxidase (1). We discuss the clinical presentation, imaging findings, and review the literature on this under-recognized disease. Molybdenum cofactor deficiency is a rare autosomal recessive inborn error of metabolism that is often fatal. More than 90% of the cases present early, in the first few days of life, with altered behaviour, altered consciousness, seizures not responding to antiseptics, hypertonia, and feeding difficulties, Severe respiratory distress requiring mechanical ventilation. Death at an early age is common, and patients who survive usually progress it usually presents with neonatal feeding problems, neonatal seizures, increased or decreased muscle

tone, ocular lens dislocation, severe intellectual disability, and death in early childhood. Milder cases have presented with lens dislocation only. To severe psychomotor delay (1). Molybdenum cofactor deficiency is typically characterized by severe neonatal convulsions not responsive to therapy. Facial dysmorphic features such as narrow bifrontal diameter, long face, puffy cheeks, and elongated palpebral fissures resemble the appearance observed in patients with hypoxic ischemic brain injury (1). Molybdenum cofactor deficiency can be easily missed as a cause of neonatal convulsions and encephalopathy (2,3); hence, it is important to maintain a high index of suspicion in order to screen for and confirm the diagnoses of this lethal disorder. More than 50% of the patients have MOCS1 mutations, followed by MOCS2, only one patient has been described with MOCS3 gene mutation (2). Accumulation of toxic levels of sulfite oxidase maybe the main pathogenic mechanism for the neurological dysfunction. All patients with MOCS2 who develop symptoms in the newborn period have typical clinical feature: refractory seizures, neurological deterioration, facial dysmorphism, feeding difficulties and early

death (4). We present the following case in accordance with the CARE reporting checklist (5) In this case, we report on the clinical presentation, MRI findings, electroencephalography, results of DNA sequencing, and 4 month follow up of a patient with genetically confirmed Molybdenum cofactor deficiency .

CASE STUDY:

A 37 week gestation full term female child 2nd by birth order was born by normal delivery, child of a third degree consanguineous marriage, born to a healthy mother at an outside institution. Birth weight was 2330 grams , head circumference 32.3 cms.. Her Apgar score was 9 and 10 at one and five minutes, respectively. Child was having normal neonatal adaptation till 3rd day of her life. After that mother noticed child is not taking feeds adequately and having vomiting after each feeds non bilious. Mother also noticed yellowish discoloration of eyes and body. She had mild respiratory distress , 1 episode of paroxysmal activity for which for which parents took the child to local practitioner and was admitted in NICU there for 12 days. symptomatic treatment was given there and discharged on oral antiepileptics. At 24 days of her life child was presented with clinical indications of hypoxic-ischaemic encephalopathy with microcephaly, seizures, tonic clonic seizures, meningitis, recurrent colds, fever, lethargy, jaundice and hypertension. episodes of tonic seizures that persisted for 1 hr , with severe respiratory distress and bluish discoloration of body. Child attended in ER, primary assessment – convulsing, lethargic, impending respiratory failure, blue – considered to be sick looking. Child started on symptomatic management. IV canula secured, Anti seizure medications, bolus given, shifted to PICU on Bag tube ventilation , necessitating anticonvulsant therapy with Phenobarbital; eventually controlled with a midazolam despite of aggressive treatment child remained

encephalopathic. As child showed severe neonatal progressive encephalopathic and raising suspicion of a metabolic cause such as Hyperammonemia, maple syrup uric acidemia, non-ketotic hyperglycinemia, Molybdenum cofactor deficiency. Investigations done at the referring institute included a cerebral ultrasound, blood ammonia, lactate, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) routine studies and CSF glycine. All were reported negative or within normal limits for age. Her USG findings revealed subarachnoid spaces with cyst in cerebral parenchyma, and USG abdomen revealed renal papillary necrosis. Her 2D ECHO findings were normal. The patient was referred to our institution for an MRI of the brain and neurological consultation. MRI picture s/o-cystic encephalomalacia with In subcortical white matter in frontoparietal and temporal Lobes with bilateral Subdural collection. Punctate white matter hemorrhage In bilateral periventricular White matter. This findings given in clinical settings given rise to a suspicion of molybdenum cofactor deficiency (MOCD)/isolated sulfite oxidase Deficiency . She is suspected to be affected with molybdenum cofactor deficiency and has been evaluated for pathogenic variations.

Later this findings were confirmed by DNA whole exom study suggestive of MOCS2 gene mutation (c 18T>G) location exon2. Child was later followed up after 2 months found to have microcephaly with overriding sutures, facial dysmorphism in the form of a narrow bifrontal diameter and deep set eyes, hypertonia with hyperreflexia and bilateral ankle clonus. The patient suffered from a severe feeding difficulty and kept on O2 at home. The remainder of her physical exam was unremarkable. Her seizures were fairly controlled on a maintenance dose of levetiracetam.

RESULT:

Raising awareness regarding this condition has significant implications regarding genetic

counseling, prognostication, and possibly medicolegal liability. We report a case confirmed by genetic testing that revealed a mutation previously unreported to the best of our knowledge. IEM is individually rare but collectively common. Though IEM is criteria for exclusion but

DISCUSSION:

Molybdenum cofactor (MoCo) biosynthesis is a highly conserved biochemical pathway resulting in the biochemical activation of molybdenum after binding the dithiolene moiety of a small organic compound called molybdopterin. The active MoCo is essential for the function of the enzymes sulphite oxidase, xanthine dehydrogenase and aldehyde oxidase in mammals (Johnson et al. 1993). The gene products of the human genes MOCS1, MOCS2, MOCS3 and GEPH are required for the biosynthesis of MoCo (Reiss 2000). The biosynthetic pathway can be divided into three consecutive steps: synthesis of precursor Z by MOCS1, formation of molybdopterin by MOCS2 and MOCS3, and finally, insertion of molybdenum by GEPH. In patients with MoCo deficiency, disease-causing mutations have been identified in MOCS1, MOCS2 and GEPH (Reiss and Johnson 2003), resulting in the corresponding complementation groups A, B and C of the deficiency which are all inherited in an autosomal-recessive fashion. Molybdenum cofactor deficiency is a severe autosomal-recessive disorder with a devastating outcome. The cofactor is the product of a complex biosynthetic pathway involving four different genes (MOCS1, MOCS2, MOCS3 and GEPH). This disorder is caused almost exclusively by mutations in the MOCS1 or MOCS2 genes. Mutations affecting this biosynthetic pathway result in a lethal phenotype manifested by progressive neurological damage via the inactivation of the molybdenum cofactor-dependent enzyme, sulphite oxidase. The neurological injury caused by Molybdenum cofactor deficiency is the result of an

as clinicians we should keep investigating as MOCD is rare but having grave prognosis once diagnosed. Molecular diagnosis and genetic counseling, Parental counselling for future pregnancy is essential. Algorithmic approach will help to clinch the diagnosis.

absence of sulfite oxidase activity leading to an accumulation of the neurotoxic metabolite (sulfite) or the deficit of the product (sulfate) (1). Sulfate is required for synthesis of sulfatide, an important component of sulfated cerebrosides required for stability of myelin. A deficit in sulfate may in theory result in unstable myelin and subsequent neurologic dysfunction. The normal results of sulfatide analysis in a case of isolated sulfite oxidase deficiency argue against this mechanism of injury (6). Sulfite can cause a reduction in intracellular ATP resulting in an "energy crisis." This is supported by brain MRI data similar to that seen in hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy, and by data from a rat model of sulfite neurotoxicity reported by Zhang, et al (7). The clinical phenotype of both Molybdenum cofactor deficiency and sulfite oxidase deficiency is very similar (1) and supports a common pathway of sulfite mediated neuronal toxicity. Our case highlights several important aspects. Presentation as severe encephalopathy after ruling out sepsis, meningitis. Molybdenum cofactor deficiency is yet another one of many heterogeneous etiologies of this epileptic syndrome that is probably under-recognized (2,9). Second is the brain MRI appearance of cystic encephalomalacia, extensive subcortical and periventricular white matter loss and cystic changes. This is similar to appearance reported by other authors such as Appignani, et al, Schuirer, et al, and Ngu, et al who reported the brain MRI findings in cases of Molybdenum cofactor deficiency. Head imaging may demonstrate loss of gray and white matter differentiation, gyral swelling, sulci injury (typically assessed by evaluating the depth of focal lesional injury within

the sulci), diffusely elevated T2-weighted signal, and panlobar diffusion restriction throughout the forebrain and midbrain with relative sparing of the brain stem. Brain imaging may be normal or may demonstrate T2-weighted hyperintense or cystic lesions in the globus pallidus, thinning of the corpus callosum, and cerebellar atrophy, described a diffuse pattern of brain atrophy with arrested development of myelination and destructive as well as cystic white matter changes (10, 11, 12). Although neither the clinical presentation nor the MRI appearance is pathognomonic for Molybdenum cofactor deficiency, we suggest that the combination of both in the absence of documented hypoxic ischemic injury is characteristic enough to warrant screening for Molybdenum cofactor deficiency. Third is the close mimicry of Molybdenum cofactor clinical picture to neonatal hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy. Topku, et al, have previously reported on three cases of molybdenum cofactor deficiency presenting as hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy (13). It is particularly important to distinguish those with MoCD from those with hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) because of the potential use of fosdenopterin (NULIBRY®) for treatment of MOCS1-related MoCD.

Clinical Characteristics: More than 100 individuals with a molybdenum cofactor deficiency have been identified [Misko et al 2020; Authors, personal observations]. As is the case for many inborn errors of metabolism, MoCD represents a spectrum, with some individuals experiencing significant signs and symptoms in the neonatal period and early infancy (termed early-onset or severe MoCD) and others developing signs and symptoms in childhood or adulthood (termed late-onset or mild MoCD). More than 100 individuals with a molybdenum cofactor deficiency have been identified [Misko et al 2020; Authors, personal observations]. As is the case for many inborn errors of metabolism, MoCD represents a spectrum, with some individuals experiencing significant signs and symptoms in the neonatal

period and early infancy (termed early-onset or severe MoCD) and others developing signs and symptoms in childhood or adulthood (termed late-onset or mild MoCD). Acute encephalopathy. Intractable seizures, poor feeding, Hyperekplexia (excessive startle reaction to loud noises, touch, or movement), apnea, pyramidal and extrapyramidal dysfunction. Severe developmental delay / intellectual disability, acquired microcephaly, nonspecific craniofacial dysmorphic features like ophthalmologic manifestations (e.g., ectopia lentis). Affected individuals typically present in the first days of life (median 1 day; range 1-50 days) with severe encephalopathy, including refractory seizures, opisthotonos, axial hypotonia and appendicular hypertonia, feeding difficulties, and apnea [Misko et al 2020]. Prenatal and birth histories are usually unremarkable, though up to 40% of affected individuals have Apgar scores <7 at one minute with subsequent improvement at five and ten minutes. Lack of a sentinel event in the perinatal period and a delay between birth and the onset of symptoms help distinguish MoCD from neonatal hypoxic ischemic injury. MoCD primarily affects the central nervous system without involvement of the peripheral nervous system. Affected individuals develop severe psychomotor impairment, spastic quadriplegia, and extrapyramidal rigidity over the first months of life. The severity of cognitive and motor impairment is consistent with the catastrophic degeneration of the cortical and subcortical structures in virtually all affected individuals. Affected individuals may also display nystagmus, myoclonic jerks, or hyperekplexia (excessive startle reaction to loud noises, touch, or movement) with or without concurrent seizures [Macaya et al 2005, Zaki et al 2016]. Manifestations of neonatal hyperekplexia include abnormal responses to auditory, visual, and somatosensory stimuli such as exaggerated startle response and tonic spasms. The tonic spasms may mimic generalized tonic seizures, resulting in apnea without electrographic seizure.

Early-Onset or Severe MoCD ;Affected individuals typically present in the first days of life (median 1 day; range 1-50 days) with severe encephalopathy, including refractory seizures, opisthotonos, axial hypotonia and appendicular hypertonia, feeding difficulties, and apnea [Misko et al 2020]. Prenatal and birth histories are usually unremarkable, though up to 40% of affected individuals have Apgar scores <7 at one minute with subsequent improvement at five and ten minutes. Lack of a sentinel event in the perinatal period and a delay between birth and the onset of symptoms help distinguish MoCD from neonatal hypoxic ischemic injury.early-onset MoCD is poor, with about 75% succumbing in infancy to secondary complications of their neurologic disability (i.e., pneumonia). Late-onset MoCD is typically characterized by milder symptoms, such as acute neurologic decompensation in the setting of infection. Episodes vary in nature but commonly consist of altered mental status, dystonia, choreoathetosis, ataxia, nystagmus, and fluctuating hypotonia and hypertonia. These features may improve after resolution of the inciting infection or progress in a gradual or stochastic manner over the lifetime. Brain imaging may be normal or may demonstrate T2-weighted hyperintense or cystic lesions in the globus pallidus, thinning of the corpus callosum, and cerebellar atrophy.

Table 01)

Clinical presentation and morphological signs In mOCD.

Neurologic signs. MoCD primarily affects the central nervous system without involvement of the peripheral nervous system. Affected individuals develop severe psychomotor impairment, spastic quadriplegia, and extrapyramidal rigidity over the first months of life. The severity of cognitive and motor impairment is consistent with the catastrophic degeneration of the cortical and

subcortical structures in virtually all affected individuals. Affected individuals may also display nystagmus, myoclonic jerks, or hyperekplexia (excessive startle reaction to loud noises, touch, or movement) with or without concurrent seizures [Macaya et al 2005, Zaki et al 2016]. Manifestations of neonatal hyperekplexia include abnormal responses to auditory, visual, and somatosensory stimuli such as exaggerated startle response and tonic spasms. The tonic spasms may mimic generalized tonic seizures, resulting in apnea without electrographic seizure. Molybdenum cofactor deficiency (MoCD) represents a spectrum, with some individuals experiencing significant signs and symptoms in the neonatal period and early infancy (termed early-onset or severe MoCD) and others developing signs and symptoms in childhood or adulthood (termed late-onset or mild MoCD). Individuals with early-onset MoCD typically present in the first days of life with severe encephalopathy, including refractory seizures, opisthotonos, axial and appendicular hypotonia, feeding difficulties, and apnea. It becomes critical that such clinical presentations are not assumed to be caused by undocumented hypoxic ischemic injury, particularly that these patients are usually products of healthy pregnancies and are born with adequate Apgar scores (1). Losing the diagnoses to the assumption of hypoxic ischemic injury may have significant consequences: the opportunity to counsel parents regarding the risk of recurrence in future pregnancies is lost, the attribution to hypoxic ischemic injury may be grounds for litigation and malpractice claims, and the future progression of the disease may not be closely followed due to the assumption of a static brain injury.

Establishing the Diagnosis

Variable course of stochastic regression, sometimes around infection

Suggestive laboratory findings .Elevated taurine and decreased cystine concentrations on plasma amino acid analysis.Decreased plasma total

homocysteine concentration. Elevated xanthine and hypoxanthine concentrations on urine pyrimidine analysis. Decreased plasma uric acid concentration. Elevated urine levels of S-sulfocysteine and thiosulfate on targeted measurement.

Brain MRI findings

Acute Diffusion restriction and elevated T2-weighted signal throughout the cortical ribbon, subcortical white matter, basal ganglia, midbrain, and to a lesser extent the pons and medulla. Gyral swelling. In some affected individuals in the first days of life, imaging features suggestive of prenatal-associated injury. Chronic Atrophy of the cortex, subcortical white matter, basal ganglia, corpus callosum, and/or cerebellum. High T1-weighted signal in the basal ganglia. Cystic leukomalacia. Ulegyria (mushroom-shaped morphology of gyri resulting from injury and contraction of sulci; also seen in neonatal hypoxic ischemic injury). Brain MRI findings. It is particularly important to distinguish those with MoCD from those with hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) because of the potential use of fosdenopterin (NULIBRY®) for treatment of MOCS1-related MoCD (Treatment – Targeted Therapies). Radiographic features present in those with MoCD but typically absent in those with HIE include the following: Mega cisterna magna or Dandy-Walker malformation. Hypoplastic/atrophic corpus callosum or cerebellum. Evidence of prenatal brain degeneration present at the time of birth (cortical atrophy, cystic leukomalacia, or basal ganglia degeneration). While these features are inconsistently present across all individuals with early-onset or severe MoCD, their presence should suggest MoCD in the right clinical setting. Absence of these findings does not exclude the diagnosis of MoCD.

MR spectroscopy:

Lactate doublet. Glutamine-glutamate (Glx) peak. Family history is consistent with autosomal

recessive inheritance (e.g., affected sibs and/or parental consanguinity). Absence of a positive family history does not preclude the diagnosis. Acute findings in the neonatal period closely resemble those observed in individuals with hypoxic-ischemic injury. Loss of gray and white matter differentiation, gyral swelling, sulci injury (typically assessed by evaluating the depth of the focal lesion injury within the sulci), diffusely elevated T2-weighted signal, and panlobar diffusion restriction are present throughout the forebrain and midbrain, with relative sparing of the brain stem. Prominent lactate doublets and a glutamine/glutamate peak are frequently observed on MR spectroscopy in affected areas. Over the course of several weeks, severe cortical atrophy, cystic leukomalacia, and degeneration of the basal ganglia develop. In contrast to hypoxic-ischemic injury, diffusion restriction is still present in areas of remaining parenchyma through the chronic phase of disease. Progressive thinning of the corpus callosum and cerebellar atrophy also develop with time [Vijayakumar et al 2011].

Gene-targeted testing requires that the clinician determine which gene(s) are likely involved, whereas genomic testing does not. Individuals with the distinctive findings described in Suggestive Findings are likely to be diagnosed using gene-targeted testing whereas those in whom the diagnosis of MoCD has not been considered are more likely to be diagnosed using genomic testing. The diagnosis of molybdenum cofactor deficiency is established by identification of biallelic pathogenic (or likely pathogenic) variants in GPHN, MOCS1, MOCS2, or MOCS3 or when unavailable, of significantly reduced activity of the enzyme sulfite oxidase in cultured fibroblasts. However, due to low expression of sulfite oxidase in fibroblasts, differentiation between total and partial loss of enzyme activity is difficult to discern. Because of its high sensitivity, molecular genetic testing typically obviates the need for enzymatic

testing and thus is the preferred diagnostic test for MoCD. Per ACMG/AMP variant interpretation guidelines, the terms "pathogenic variants" and "likely pathogenic variants" are synonymous in a clinical setting, meaning that both are considered diagnostic and both can be used for clinical decision making [Richards et al 2015]. Reference to "pathogenic variants" in this section is understood to include any likely pathogenic variants. (2) Identification of biallelic variants of uncertain significance (or of one known pathogenic variant and one variant of uncertain significance) does not establish or rule out the diagnosis. Molecular genetic testing approaches can include gene-targeted testing (multigene panel) and comprehensive genomic testing (exome sequencing, exome array, genome sequencing) depending on the phenotype.

A neonatal seizure, epilepsy, or neurodegenerative multigene panel that includes GPHN, MOCS1, MOCS2, MOCS3, and other genes of interest (see Differential Diagnosis) is most likely to identify the genetic cause of the condition while limiting identification of variants of uncertain significance and pathogenic variants in genes that do not explain the underlying phenotype. Note: (1) The genes included in the panel and the diagnostic sensitivity of the testing used for each gene vary by laboratory and are likely to change over time. (2) Some multigene panels may include genes not associated with the condition discussed in this GeneReview. (3) In some laboratories, panel options may include a custom laboratory-designed panel and/or custom phenotype-focused exome analysis that includes genes specified by the clinician. (4) Methods used in a panel may include sequence analysis, deletion/duplication analysis, and/or other non-sequencing-based tests low uric acid levels in the blood, and as in our case, urine, should point to the diagnoses of molybdenum cofactor deficiency (14). This along with detection of sulfite in fresh urine dipstick should help distinguish both entities and prompt further confirmation. While these features

are inconsistently present across all individuals with early-onset or severe MoCD, their presence should suggest MoCD in the right clinical setting. Absence of these findings does not exclude the diagnosis of MoCD. Moreover, emerging research on animal models provides hope for future availability of effective treatments in humans. Kugler, et al, recently reported on the long term rescue of a mouse model of Molybdenum cofactor deficiency type A, the most frequent form of this autosomal recessive disorder, by adenoassociated virus mediated gene transfer (5), this provides hope for future therapeutic options in homozygous humans, hence, increased awareness and early identification of these patients may then have significant implications. Fourth are some atypical features of our case such as the normal lactate and the absence of lens dislocation; the former being usually elevated, and the later being found in nearly all patients after neonatal period, although Parini, et al, have reported a case that developed lens dislocation as late as eight years of age (15). Atypical presentations of molybdenum cofactor deficiency have also been reported by others, such as a case of molybdenum cofactor deficiency associated with Dandy-Walker malformation presenting with severe metabolic acidosis and intracranial hemorrhage (16), also a case presenting as neonatal hyperekplexia (17), indicating a wide spectrum of clinical presentations in these patients. Finally, our patient's genotype revealed MOCS2 mutation (c 18T>G) location exon2 this is a novel mutation not previously reported to the best of our knowledge. A homozygous nonsense variation in exon 2 of the MOCS2 gene that results in a stop codon and premature truncation of the protein at codon 6 (p.Tyr6Ter; ENST00000527216.5) was detected. The observed variation has previously been reported (as Y11*) in patients affected with Molybdenum cofactor deficiency B and has been classified as pathogenic in the ClinVar database. This variant has not been reported in the 1000 genomes databases and has a minor allele

frequency of 0%, 0.01% in the gnomAD and in our internal databases respectively. The reference codon is conserved across species. OMIM phenotype: Molybdenum cofactor deficiency B is caused by homozygous or compound heterozygous mutations in the MOCS2 gene. This disorder is characterized by neonatal onset of intractable seizures, opisthotonus, and facial dysmorphism associated with hypouricemia and elevated urinary sulfite levels. Affected individuals show severe neurologic damage. Deletions of sulfite oxidase genes have been reported to have led to death at ten weeks (18), and 32 months of age (19). On the other hand, Leimkuhler, et al, have reported on mutations in MOSC1 and MOSC2 which create a stop codon, or abolish the binding ability of molybdopterin synthase (20), the clinical significance of these in vitro characterizations warrants more study. Another important factor in the genetic aspect is providing for prenatal genetic analysis in cases of molybdenum cofactor deficiency, as first reported by Reiss, et al (21), this is particularly important in consanguineous marriages.

Related Genetic Counseling.

Family planning : The optimal time for determination of genetic risk and discussion of the availability of prenatal/preimplantation genetic testing is before pregnancy.

It is appropriate to offer genetic counseling (including discussion of potential risks to offspring and reproductive options) to young adults who are carriers or are at risk of being carriers the future, consideration should be given to banking DNA from probands in whom a molecular diagnosis has not been confirmed (i.e., the causative pathogenic mechanism is unknown). For more information, see Huang et al [2022].

Prenatal Testing and Preimplantation Genetic Testing

The deficiencies can be diagnosed prenatally by monitoring sulfite oxidase activity in chorionic villus sampling (CVS) tissue. In those families in which the specific defects have been identified, diagnosis can be achieved by mutation analysis or linkage studies directed at affected. Once the MoCD-causing pathogenic variants have been identified in an affected family member, prenatal and preimplantation genetic testing are possible.

Differences in perspective may exist among medical professionals and within families regarding the use of prenatal testing. While most centers would consider use of prenatal testing to be a personal decision, discussion of these issues may be helpful.

CONCLUSION:

MoCD is a rare autosomal recessive inborn error of metabolism that was firstly described by Duran et al. We report a novel mutation in a newborn with typical clinical and radiological features of Molybdenum cofactor deficiency, and discuss the clues that raise suspicion for the diagnoses. Although not pathognomonic, we suggest that in the absence of a clear history of hypoxic ischemic injury, all newborns presenting with a triad of early seizures, encephalopathy, and destructive white matter cystic changes should be screened for Molybdenum cofactor deficiency, particularly with family history of consanguinity. Encouraging results of rescue therapies for animal models of Molybdenum cofactor deficiency provide hope of this becoming a treatable disorder in the future.

Declaration:

There was no source of funding in our study and there was no any conflict of interest in this study.

Acknowledgement:

This was a case report study conducted over a period of 4 months. Informed consent was taken before study was being proceeded.

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Molybdenum Cofactor Deficiency: Report of a New Case and Literature Review Waseem M. Fathalla*

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Molybdenum cofactor deficiency: report of three cases presenting as hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy M Topcu 1, T Coskun, G Haliloglu, I Saatci.

Molybdenum cofactor deficiency: review of 12 cases (MoCD and review) Erhan Bayram 1, Yasemin Topcu, Pakize Karakaya, Uluc Yis, Handan Cakmakci, Kimiyoshi Ichida, Semra Hiz Kurul

Molybdenum cofactor deficiency: Review of 12 cases (MoCD and review) Author links open overlay panel Erhan Bayram a, Yasemin Topcu a, Pakize Karakaya a, Uluc Yis a, Handan Cakmakci b, Kimiyoshi Ichida c, Semra Hiz Kurul a.

Case Report: Compound Heterozygous Variants in MOCS3 Identified in a Chinese Infant With Molybdenum Cofactor Deficiency Qi Tian^{1†}, Yang Cao^{2†}, Li Shu^{1,3,4}, Yongjun Chen⁵, Ying Peng¹, Yaqin Wang⁶, Yuanyuan Chen⁷, Hua Wang^{1,3*} and Xiao Mao^{1,3*}

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20) Investigation of molybdenum cofactor deficiency due to MOCS2 deficiency in a newborn baby Author links open overlay panel Matthew Edwards a b, Juliane Roeper c d, Catherine Allgood a b, Raymond Chin a b, Jose Santamaria c d, Flora Wong e f, Guenter Schwarz c d, John Whitehall .